

Task Force on Machine Learning (TF-ML) Report

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1. Context and Objectives of the Task Force

CORDEX activities are organized both by geographical regions (14 domains) and by thematic initiatives (Flagship Pilot Studies, FPS). Task Forces (TFs) are a new short-term instrument (maximum duration of one year) established to plan and accelerate progress on emerging scientific and technical challenges. Their main role is to review the state of the art, develop focused guidance, and propose concrete actions for how CORDEX should address these challenges, providing recommendations to the CORDEX SAT for future implementation.

Machine Learning (ML) is a rapidly evolving interdisciplinary field with significant potential to advance climate downscaling, providing innovative approaches to enhance the performance and scalability of downscaling techniques. Promising results have already emerged, demonstrating its capability to complement and extend standard methods. CORDEX regional activities and Flagship Pilot Studies (FPS) are playing an active role in advancing these developments, contributing to the exploration of new ML downscaling approaches and methods, and fostering collaboration across the climate science community. Continued efforts in this area are expected to drive further innovation and improve our understanding of regional climate processes. Effective coordination across key initiatives is crucial for addressing challenges such as establishing standards, conducting intercomparison and evaluation, identifying and advancing critical research gaps, and organizing collaborative ensemble production.

Machine Learning could help address several long-standing challenges faced by CORDEX, most of which stem from the computational demands and practical limitations of running Regional Climate Models (RCMs). First, the high computational cost of running RCMs is a barrier to producing large downscaled ensembles of climate projections, thus limiting the sampling uncertainty across GCM–RCM combinations (model uncertainty), emission scenarios, and internal variability at fine spatial scales. Second, generating coordinated ensembles is particularly difficult in resource-limited regions, resulting in inequities across CORDEX domains due to limited computational resources, data infrastructure, and expertise; more affordable ML approaches could help reduce this gap and promote wider community participation. Third, progress toward kilometre-scale, convection-permitting modeling—a key scientific priority—remains computationally prohibitive, restricting CORDEX’s ability to deliver global high-resolution information. Fourth, although CORDEX has developed extensive activity in empirical–statistical downscaling (ESD), these approaches require expert supervision to adapt to specific regions and depend on high-quality observational datasets for training, which limits their scalability. As a consequence, ESD has mostly been applied at regional to local scales and has not yet overcome the structural limitations described above. ML-based methods could help reverse this situation by introducing automated approaches that require minimal human intervention and are suitable for continental-scale applications (Baño-Medina et al. 2022).

The primary objective of the CORDEX Task Force (TF) on Machine Learning (TF-ML) is to develop a strategic plan for coordinating machine learning-based downscaling activities. This will require collaboration and coordination with relevant external initiatives, which will be identified through a landscaping activity to assess the current status of the field. Within CORDEX, the Task Force will work closely with ongoing regional, FPS and TF activities, particularly the TF on Convection, to align km-scale downscaling activities. Additionally, it aims to coordinate contributions to CORDEX-CMIP6/7 downscaling experiments, promote best practices, and facilitate knowledge exchange to address key challenges in the field.

2. Structure of the Task Force

The final structure of the Task Force was approved at the second meeting (4 March 2025) and is presented in the table below. Given the strong links with the Task Force on Convection-Permitting Modelling, several members from that group were also designated as liaisons.

José Manuel Gutiérrez	Co-Coordinator. Europe. ESD/ML and emulators
Neelesh Rampal	Co-Coordinator. Australasia. ESD/ML and emulators
María Laura Bettolli	South America / POC. ESD/ML
Melissa Bukovsky	North America / SAT. RCM, ESD
Antoine Doury	Europe. Emulators
Jorge Baño Medina	Europe / North America. ESD/ML and emulators
Pedro M. M. Soares	Europe / Africa: RCM, ESD/ML and emulators
Quang-Van Doan	Asia. RCM, ESD and urban climate
Alain Tamoffo Tchio	Africa. ESD
Ramón Fuentes	Europe and South America. ESD/ML
Peter Watson	Europe. Emulators
Fatima Driouech	Africa. ESD/ML
Andrew Orr	Polar. RCM, ESD
Koji Dairaku	Asia. ESD
Kyo Lee	NorthAmerica. ESD/ML
Ben Booth	Europe. RCM, Emulators
Stefan Sobolowski	Link to convection TF, RCM and emulators
Lizzie Kendon	Link to convection TF, RCM and emulators
Erika Coppola	Link to convection TF, RCM and emulators
Jason Evans	Link to convection TF, RCM

Table 1. Members of the TF indicating region of interest (and role in CORDEX, if any) and expertise in RCM, ESD/ML and emulators.

3. The Landscape of ML Downscaling

This section provides an overview of research progress in ML-based climate downscaling, with the aim of mapping the current landscape and clarifying CORDEX's potential role in this rapidly evolving field. It synthesizes key models, methodologies, and studies from the scientific literature, with particular emphasis on approaches relevant for climate change applications.

Early ML-based downscaling studies focused primarily on **super-resolution (SR)** techniques, training models to transform coarse-resolution fields into finer-resolution outputs using paired datasets (e.g., low- and high-resolution reanalysis or model simulations). Although extensively explored, these techniques generally do not

incorporate large-scale atmospheric predictors and therefore do not condition the downscaling function on large-scale circulation. As a result, SR techniques behave more like bias-adjustment tools than physically conditioned downscaling methods and are not considered further in this report.

More advanced work follows the **empirical-statistical downscaling (ESD)** paradigm, also known as observational downscaling, training models directly on observational (historical) datasets to learn relationships between large-scale predictors and local-scale climate variables. While ML-based ESD approaches have shown promising performance (see González-Abad et al. 2025), their strong reliance on past observations raises concerns about their ability to extrapolate to future, warmer climates where predictor-predictand relationships may change. Evaluation is also challenging, as model skill cannot easily be assessed outside the observational range on which the models are trained. In addition, observational uncertainty, spatial coverage gaps, and inconsistencies across regions pose further limitations for robust model training and intercomparison. A comprehensive review of these developments and challenges is provided by Rampal et al. (2024).

A more recent and rapidly growing line of research focuses on ML-based RCM **emulators** designed to reproduce the downscaling behavior of regional climate models (RCMs). These emulators can be trained using both historical and future climate simulations, allowing for explicit evaluation under future climates and mitigating the extrapolation limitations inherent to ESD approaches. Recent studies have shown that emulators can reproduce key climate statistics, extremes and their climate change signals (Rampal et al., 2024). However, because emulators are typically trained on specific GCM–RCM pairs, they raise important questions about transferability: whether a model trained with one driving GCM or in one region can generalize reliably to others with different climatic regimes, physical parameterizations, or boundary conditions. Achieving robust transferability across scenarios, GCMs, and regions (each posing increasing levels of difficulty) remains an open challenge and is essential for their use within coordinated frameworks such as CORDEX. Recent developments and remaining challenges in climate emulation are reviewed in Kendon et al. (2025).

To better characterize the evolution and current state of AI-based climate downscaling relative to traditional ESD and RCM methodologies, we conducted a **meta-analysis of the scientific literature**, combining keywords related to downscaling (e.g., *statistical downscaling*, *regional climate modeling*) with those related to AI (e.g., *machine learning*, *deep learning*, *artificial intelligence*, *emulators*) across titles and abstracts. Trends in these fields are shown in Figure 1 (note that ESD counts also include studies related to bias adjustment).

Figure 1. Evolution of bibliographic publications for (a) downscaling (red) and AI-based downscaling (blue), with lighter shades indicating studies specifically focused on climate applications, and (b) the distribution of AI-based downscaling studies across methodological categories: super-resolution (SR), deep learning (DL), RCM emulators (RCM-emul), and other AI approaches (AI-other), including random forests, support vector machines, Gaussian processes, and related methods.

These figures show that the number of studies on climate downscaling is small (~100 in 2025) compared with the broad downscaling context. A summary of recent publications focusing on downscaling climate projections are described below.

Studies by Continent

- **Europe:** 7 studies (Spain, UK, France, Germany, Portugal)
- **Asia:** 5 studies (China, India, Taiwan)
- **North America:** 2 studies (USA)
- **South America:** 3 studies (Argentina)
- **Oceania:** 4 studies (New Zealand, Australia)

Most Used ML Models

- **CNN & Dense Networks:** 5 studies
- **U-Net:** 5 studies
- **GAN:** 3 studies
- **RNN:** 2 studies
- **Diffusion Models:** 3 studies
- **Hybrid RCM (Physics + AI):** 1 study
- **Graph Neural Networks:** 1 study

While most deep-learning downscaling studies have been led by universities and public research institutes, several major technology and industry laboratories have recently begun exploring AI-based downscaling, mainly in the context of weather forecasting, and often through the application of foundation models or diffusion-based techniques. Examples include:

- **NVIDIA** is one of the few major technology companies directly developing AI-based climate downscaling tools through its Earth-2 platform. A central component is **CorrDiff**, a diffusion-based generative model designed for downscaling weather and climate fields (e.g., from 25 km to convection-permitting scales; Mardani et al. 2024). CorrDiff is deployed as part of the Earth-2 microservices and is used in some weather forecasting applications.
- **IBM** has also engaged directly in AI-based climate and weather downscaling exploring the use of foundation models for downscaling, for instance **Prithvi WxC** foundation model, developed in collaboration with NASA (e.g., Schumde et al. 2024).
- **Microsoft** contributes indirectly to climate downscaling through its **AI for Earth** programme and its Earth-system foundation models. ClimaX, developed by Microsoft Research, is a general deep-learning framework that lists climate downscaling among its intended applications. In addition, AI for Earth has supported external ML/statistical downscaling projects and hosts downscaled datasets through the Planetary Computer (Gergel et al. 2024).
- Google **DeepMind** has made major advances in AI weather forecasting but has not directly focused on climate downscaling to date. However, **Google Research** has recently initiated work on diffusion-based downscaling approaches (Lopez-Gomez et al. 2025).

4. Intercomparison and Benchmarking Activities

While ML-based downscaling approaches show great promise, systematic evaluation and benchmarking remain major gaps in the field. Most existing studies rely on different datasets, predictors, temporal resolutions, and geographic domains, making

meaningful intercomparison extremely difficult. CORDEX has substantial experience coordinating intercomparison and evaluation activities. Notably, CORDEX organized a major ESD intercomparison experiment, supported by community tools such as the VALUE evaluation framework (Gutiérrez et al. 2019), demonstrating the value of coordinated and transparent assessment exercises.

In the AI community, intercomparison activities are typically structured through benchmarks providing standardized datasets, metrics, and protocols designed to enable reproducible and fair model comparison (Dueben, 2022). Benchmarks play a central role in accelerating progress, identifying methodological strengths and weaknesses, and establishing good practices. Bringing similar rigor to ML-based climate downscaling will therefore be essential for developing trustworthy and operationally relevant methods. Although some benchmark datasets for downscaling have been proposed (e.g., Langguth et al. 2024), none provide a comprehensive framework tailored to climate change applications, particularly one capable of assessing generalization to future climates, extrapolation skill, and transferability across regions and driving models. As a result, current efforts remain fragmented, and community standards and best practices are still in early development.

Recognizing these gaps, the TF has initiated a first benchmarking experiment (**CORDEX-ML-Bench**) explicitly designed for climate applications. The overarching goal is to establish a reproducible and extensible benchmarking framework that will serve as the foundation for future community-wide intercomparison exercises and the development of best-practice guidelines within the CORDEX program. Looking ahead, subsequent benchmarking efforts could be tailored to address specific challenges and research gaps identified in collaboration with other CORDEX communities. This first benchmarking initiative focuses on the key challenges of ML-based climate downscaling, with particular emphasis on extrapolation and transferability, two fundamental issues that determine the reliability of AI models under changing climate conditions.

4.1. A first CORDEX ML Benchmark (CORDEX-ML-Bench)

The first benchmark targets daily temporal resolution and a standard 0.11° spatial scale, consistent with current CORDEX experimental protocols, while being designed for future extensions, including sub-daily and convection-permitting (km-scale) downscaling, allowing coordination and collaboration across CORDEX initiatives. The CORDEX-ML-Bench includes three climatically distinct regions, the European Alps, South Africa, and New Zealand, selected to represent contrasting climatic drivers and conditions. These domains serve as illustrative starting points, and the framework is intentionally structured to be expandable to additional regions covering diverse climate regimes (e.g., tropical or monsoon areas). By providing harmonized input and reference datasets, the benchmark enables consistent, reproducible comparison across methods and offers a foundation for a globally extendable, multi-domain downscaling evaluation suite. Figure 2 shows the three domains in the first benchmark, the two training experiments (ESD and Emulator), the AI models tested, and the evaluation periods used.

CORDEX-ML-Bench: Experimental Design

A schematic overview of the benchmarking pipeline for data-driven regional climate downscaling.

Figure 2: CORDEX-ML-Bench Experimental Design. The top panel provides a schematic overview of the benchmark, summarizing the spatial domains, training configurations, machine-learning architectures, and evaluation periods. The bottom panel shows the regional domains in greater detail, including the coarse-resolution predictor boundaries (dashed black lines), the nested high-resolution target domains (solid red lines), and the underlying surface elevation (color scale in meters). Insets highlight each region with predictor and target grids overlaid on regional orography.

The dataset is publicly available on Zenodo as zip files (~5 GB per domain), and the specifications for each domain are shown in Table 2. Each domain includes data from one Regional Climate Model (RCM) driven by two Global Climate Models (GCMs): one for training and testing, and another exclusively for testing transferability.

Domain	Resolution	Target Variables	Target Grid	Predictor Variables	Predictor Grid	Static Fields
New Zealand (NZ)	0.11°	Tasmax, Pr	128 × 128	u, v, q, t, z at 850, 700, 500 hPa (15 variables)	16 × 16 (2°)	Orography (128 × 128; 0.11°)
Europe (ALPS)	0.11°	Tasmax, Pr	128 × 128	u, v, q, t, z at 850, 700, 500 hPa	16 × 16 (2°)	Orography
South Africa (SA)	0.10°	Tasmax, Pr	128 × 128	u, v, q, t, z at 850, 700, 500 hPa	16 × 16 (2°)	Orography

Table 2: Specifications of the three pilot domains used in CORDEX-ML-Bench.

As an example, we describe below in Table 3 the dataset generated for the Alps region (Europe), aligned with the Convection Flagship Pilot Studies (FPS) and susceptible for a future extension considering km-scale convection permitting simulations (from the FPS).

GCM / RCM	CNRM (GCM), Aladin63 (RCM) — from CORDEX-CMIP5
Predictors	Z, T, U, V, Q, relative humidity at 1000, 850, 700, 500, 200 hPa (optional); 30 years RCM-U (ALADIN-CNRM, 1.5°, ~150 MB): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CNRM-ALADIN63_historical_r1i1p1_1981-2000.nc (50 MB) • CNRM-ALADIN63_rcp85_r1i1p1_2041-2060.nc (50 MB) • CNRM-ALADIN63_rcp85_r1i1p1_2081-2100.nc (50 MB) GCM (CNRM, 1.5°, ~150 MB)
Predictands	tas, pr; 30 years; RCM: ALADIN-CNRM (~0.112°, ~2 GB × 2) Main driving GCM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CNRM-ALADIN63_historical_r1i1p1_1981-2000_v2.nc (2 × 300 MB) • CNRM-ALADIN63_rcp85_r1i1p1_2041-2060_v2.nc (2 × 300 MB) • CNRM-ALADIN63_rcp85_r1i1p1_2081-2100_v2.nc (2 × 300 MB) Second driving GCM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ***-ALADIN63_historical_r1i1p1_1981-2000_v2.nc (2 × 300 MB) • ***-ALADIN63_rcp85_r1i1p1_2041-2060_v2.nc (2 × 300 MB) • ***-ALADIN63_rcp85_r1i1p1_2081-2100_v2.nc (2 × 300 MB)
Future Extension (km-scale)	CPM: AROME-ALADIN-CNRM (0.0316° × 0.0224°, ~16.8 GB + 8.4 GB) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CNRM-AROME41t1-ALP3_historical_r1i1p1_1996-2005.nc (2 × 4.2 GB) • CNRM-AROME41t1-ALP3_rcp85_r1i1p1_2041-2050.nc (2 × 4.2 GB) • CNRM-AROME41t1-ALP3_rcp85_r1i1p1_2090-2099.nc (2 × 4.2 GB)

Table 3: Specifications of the ALPS training data used in CORDEX-ML-Bench. Further information for the domains will be provided in the companioning manuscript.

For each selected region, the benchmark focuses on a single RCM and includes carefully structured training and testing data derived from dynamically downscaled Global Climate Models (GCMs), enabling systematic analysis of emulator performance in both historical and future climates.

The dataset provides two core training experiments:

1. **ESD Pseudo-Reality (1961–1980)**. A 20-year historical training period using a single GCM (e.g., ACCESS-CM2 for NZ), designed to mimic ESD training.
2. **Emulator Hist+Future (1961–1980 + 2081–2100)**. A more comprehensive 40-year training period combining historical and future climates. This experiment supports evaluation of extrapolative skill, including transferability across GCMs.

Both setups will be tested with and without topography as a predictor (when possible).

For each training setup, the dataset enables evaluation across multiple test periods and inference conditions:

- **Historical (1981–2000)**: For both perfect and imperfect inference.
- **Mid-century (2041–2060) and End-century (2081–2100)**: To assess extrapolation to future climates, including hard transferability scenarios using unseen GCMs.

The dataset supports several benchmarking configurations:

- **PP cross-validation**: Same GCM used in training and testing.
- **Imperfect inference**: Same GCM but different realizations or noise.
- **Transferability testing**: Inference using a different GCM than the training set.
- **Change signal evaluation**: Assessment of climate change response in future periods.

The datasets have been generated and contributing groups have started the training activities to participate in this first benchmark:

<https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/ml-benchmark>

5. Proposed Actions and Way Forward

A key strength of CORDEX lies in its coordinated structure across regions (14 continental domains) and activities (FPSs, TFs). Over the past decade, this structure has supported the development of strong communities of practice and provided common guidance, protocols, and evaluation frameworks that unify diverse research groups and experimental designs worldwide. This coordination has enabled robust intercomparison studies, facilitated knowledge exchange across domains, and strengthened the credibility and usability of regional climate information for operational climate services.

Given this experience and existing infrastructure, CORDEX is uniquely positioned to coordinate emerging benchmarking activities in Machine-Learning-based downscaling, working in close collaboration with existing CORDEX structures and engaging the broader WCRP community and other relevant partners.

To advance this effort, a Task Team could be established to coordinate the study of core scientific challenges to ensure robustness of ML-based climate downscaling, including extrapolation and transferability, representation of extremes, multivariate (multi-variable and spatial) consistency, and physical consistency. The following activities are proposed:

1. **Continue the CORDEX-ML-Bench intercomparison studies** addressing key scientific challenges, coordinating closely with CORDEX FPSs and TFs to ensure alignment with CORDEX activities and protocols. This is a long-term pillar of this activity since it allows to extend the intercomparison analysis to new regions, temporal and spatial scales and challenges and could also foster engagement with end-users in the series of benchmarking experiments, e.g., downscaling impact indices such heat stress.
2. Coordination of **community software tools** for data preprocessing, model training, and downscaling with ML tools. These tools would enhance reproducibility and facilitate the adoption of the battery of ML downscaling tools across the CORDEX domains.
3. **Develop capacity-building activities** to ensure that all CORDEX domains can apply reference ML methods, building on the outcomes of the benchmarking exercises and helping reduce disparities across regions.
4. **Contribute to the CMIP7 experimental framework**, providing technical input on ML-based downscaling protocols and evaluation strategies, in coordination with the CMIP7 Task Team.

5. **Coordinate the contribution of ML-based downscaling methods to CORDEX-CMIP7**, ensuring consistency, documenting best practices, and supporting integration with the broader CORDEX framework.

To implement these activities, we propose establishing a **CORDEX ML Task Team** with an initial **two-year mandate** (extendable by one additional year if CMIP7 timelines require it). The Task Team would lead the scientific coordination, develop guidance documents, and ensure alignment between MLBench activities, CORDEX domains, and the evolving CMIP7 framework.

Proposed two-year roadmap (2026–2028)

ACTIVITY	2026		2027				2028	
	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2
Establish ML Task Team	Open call · launch							
CORDEX-ML-Bench (Phase 2 onwards)		Bench Phase 2: imperfect + cross-GCM			New domains (tropical, monsoon, hi-lat)			Sub-daily & km-scale
Community software tools			Preprocessing · training · evaluation					
Capacity building		Webinar		Hackathon				
CMIP7 experimental protocol			Technical input · evaluation strategy					
CORDEX-CMIP7 ML contribution							Methods + integration	

Figure 3. Proposed timeline for the CORDEX ML Task Team and associated activities.

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